

GRAPHENE WOVEN FABRIC/EPOXY COMPOSITES WITH EXCEPTIONAL FRACTURE TOUGHNESS AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Graphene woven fabric (GWF) is synthesized by a template-based chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method. Compared to 2D graphene sheets, the GWF present unique morphological features and properties due to the lightweight graphene tubes integrated into a continuous network with a mesh configuration. Planar porous GWF/epoxy composites are prepared by directly infiltrating epoxy resin onto GWF and etching of the Ni template. These composites have a porous structure where the flexible and hollow graphene tubes are interconnected orthogonally in two perpendicular directions, totally eliminating the needs for careful dispersion and functionalization of graphene nanosheets to make composites. The composites exhibit excellent electrical conductivities, high mechanical properties and fracture toughness resulting from the well-designed graphene network structure. The effect of three different orientations of hollow graphene tubes are specifically investigated on complex fracture behavior and mechanical properties of the anisotropic composites. The new carbon material offers a potential as reinforcing filler for porous composites with interesting mechanical and multi-functional performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Interconnected graphene structures with conductive networks and large specific surface areas have recently attracted significantly attention. One of the principal drawbacks in the fabrication of graphene or graphene oxide (GO) using chemical methods is to introduce defects and impurities into the graphene sheets during exfoliation and dispersion of GO, which deteriorate the quality and properties of graphene [1]. The CVD process can avoid these issues and has become one of the most promising methods to fabricate interconnected and continuous graphene structures. The graphene acquired by CVD exhibits many other advantages, including batch production, high purity without defects or oxidation, and extremely high electrical conductivity [2]. More importantly, three-dimensional graphene foam (GF) with controlled pore sizes can be grown on a metal foam template. GF/polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) composites were fabricated by growing graphene on Ni foam and simply coating the GF with PDMS. They showed outstanding electrical, mechanical properties, and high efficiencies in electromagnetic interference shielding of about 500 dBcm³/g [2], at low graphene content less than 0.8 wt%. Cellular-structured GF/epoxy composites also showed a remarkable electrical conductivity of 3 S/cm at 0.2 wt% graphene and the corresponding flexural modulus and strength were increased by 53% and 38% [3] respectively, compared to the neat epoxy.

Apart from the porous structure of GF, GWF has a well-designed architecture in which hollow graphene tubes are cross-linked orthogonally in a planar manner. GWF [4] showed high flexibility and potential applications in strain sensors made from PDMS-based composite films and touch sensing devices [5] due to the unique crack formation and propagation mechanism of GWF with a low electrical resistance. In light of a few studies dedicated to developing the CVD process to fabricate planar GWF on a Ni template, this paper aims to identify optimized CVD parameters for GWF fabrication and to evaluate important electrical and mechanical properties of GWF/epoxy composites.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 GWF synthesis

Ni templates in the form of woven fabric (200 mesh woven from Ni wires of 56 μm in diameter, supplied by Beijing Century Woven Corporation) were cleaned with dilute hydrochloride acid, acetone and deionized (DI) water sequentially in ultrasonicator. After drying in a vacuum oven for 24 h, the Ni templates were cut into pieces of 10 cm x 5 cm, which were put into a quartz tube furnace of the CVD machine. The furnace was heated to 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in 60 min for annealing of the template under the flow of Ar (at 200 standard cubic centimeters per minute (sccm)) and H_2 (100 sccm). CH_4 was then introduced into the chamber as carbon source at the end of thermal annealing. After deposition for 20 min, the chamber was rapidly cooled down to room temperature under the flow of Ar and H_2 . The product (G/Ni-WF) was etched in 0.5 M FeCl_3 /1 M HCl solution at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h to obtain free standing GWF.

2.2 Fabrication of GWF/epoxy composites

The fabrication process of GWF/epoxy composites is schematically illustrated in Figure 1. The epoxy resin was prepared from the mixture of four components LY 1564, Aradure 1571, accelerator LY 1573 and hardener XB 3404 (supplied by Huntsman) in the weight ratio of 100:23:3:12, while acetone was used as solvent to adjust the viscosity of the resin solution. After evaporation of the solvent and degassing in a vacuum oven, the epoxy resin was infiltrated into the as produced G/Ni-WF by immersion, which was cured in a hot press to obtain ~ 100 μm thick single layer composite plates. The GWF/epoxy composites were immersed into the dilute HCl acid (3 M) at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to etch out the Ni template, followed by cleaning using DI water and drying in an oven at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight. The GWF/epoxy composites were cut into pieces according to the test sample dimensions.

Figure 1: Schematic flowchart of the fabrication processes of GWF/epoxy composites.

2.3 Characterization

An optical microscope (Olympus BX51M) and scanning electron microscopes (SEM, JEOL JSM-6390F and JEOL JSM-6700F) with a 5 kV accelerating voltage were used to characterize the morphologies of GWF and composite fracture surfaces. A field emission transmission electron microscope (FETEM, JEOL 2010F) at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV was used to characterize the morphologies of the free-standing GWF. The 2D- to G-band intensity ratios, I_{2D}/I_G , and the defect contents of GWF were evaluated on a Micro-Raman spectrometer (Renishaw MicroRaman/Photoluminescence System) with Ar laser excitation of 514.5 nm in wavelength. The tensile tests were carried out using rectangular epoxy and composites films on a universal testing machine (MTS Alliane RT-5) [6, 7].

2.4 Fracture toughness test

The fracture resistance of solid epoxy, porous epoxy and GWF/epoxy composites were characterized in mode I tension using the double edge notched tension (DENT) test. The specimens were prepared according to the specification, ASTM E399, as shown in Figure 2. The width, w , was

13 mm, the length, $2H$, was 26 mm, and the crack length to width ratio, a/w , was 0.2 [8]. The critical stress intensity factor, K_{Ic} , was calculated using Eqs. (1) and (2) when the external stress reached a critical value, σ_c , for crack propagation:

$$K_{Ic} = \sigma_c \sqrt{\pi a} F(a/w) \quad (1)$$

where $F(a/w)$ is a geometric correction factor and for a DENT specimen is given [9]:

$$F(a/w) = 1.12 + 0.41(a/w) - 4.78(a/w)^2 + 15.44(a/w)^3 \quad (2)$$

The DENT test was conducted on a universal testing machine (MTS Alliance RT/5) at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The fracture processes of epoxy and composites were *in situ* captured using a camera. The fracture surfaces were examined on a scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM-6390F).

Figure 2: Double edge notched tension (DENT) specimen geometry.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Structure of GWF

CH_4 was introduced into the CVD furnace as the carbon source under the Ar and H_2 flows after thermal annealing. The Ni template surface functioned as the catalyst for the decomposition of carbon atoms which segregated on the Ni surface to form graphene [3]. The measure of GWF quality includes the structural stability, number of graphene layer and full coverage of graphene on the template, which were carefully controlled by the mesh density of Ni template, feed rate of CH_4 and deposition time, respectively. Figure 4 shows characteristics of GWF grown on a 200 mesh Ni template using 0.5 vol% CH_4 . The Raman spectrum (Figure 2a) presents prominent G- and 2D-bands at ~ 1580 and $\sim 2700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively: the intensity of the 2D-peak was stronger than the G-peak, and the absent of D-band indicates that few-layer graphene was synthesized with no defects. The SEM image (Figure 2b) shows high quality graphene tubes that were complete without rupture or defects. An average of 4 graphene layers was found from the TEM image (Figure 2c). It was found that with increasing CH_4 feed rate from 0.5 to 3.0 vol%, the number of graphene layer increased from 4 to 12.

Figure 3: Characteristics of GWF grown with 0.5vol% CH₄: (a) Raman spectrum, (b) SEM image and (c) TEM image of freestanding GWF.

The GWF/epoxy composites had a porous structure with microcellular tubes after removing the Ni template. Porous epoxy with hollow tubes was also prepared without graphene. The porosities, ε , of porous epoxy and GWF/epoxy composites were measured from the known densities of solid epoxy (1.19 g/cm³) and graphene (2.2 g/cm³), the weight of porous structure and the graphene content, v_g , according to the equation:

$$\varepsilon = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_t}\right) \times 100\% \quad (3)[10],$$

where ρ_a and ρ_t are the apparent and true densities of the material. ρ_t is given by:

$$\rho_t = 1 / \left(\frac{v_g}{2.2 \text{ g/cm}^3} + \frac{(1-v_g)}{1.19 \text{ g/cm}^3} \right) \quad (4),$$

where v_g varied from 0.19 to 0.62 wt.%. The porosities of the porous epoxy and the GWF/epoxy composites were estimated to be 12.5 % and 12.3 % (for $v_g = 0.62$ wt%), respectively.

3.2 Electrical conductivity

With inherent high electrical conductivities, graphene has become an attractive conductive filler to be introduced into polymers to fabricate conducting polymers. Previous studies show that graphene/polymer composites prepared by simply mixing reduced GO (rGO) or graphene nanoplates (GNPs) with a polymer matrix did not show considerable enhancements in electrical conductivities [11]. In light of this, 3D graphene structures in the form of GF[3] or graphene aerogel (GA) [12] have been developed to serve as effective conductive networks so as to enhance the electrical properties of the composites while avoiding agglomeration of fillers in the polymer.

Figure 4 (a) shows the in-plane electrical conductivities of single layer GWF/epoxy composites. Compared to the neat epoxy resin ($\sim 10^{-12}$ S/cm) [13], the electrical conductivity of the composite with 0.19 wt% graphene surged to 0.15 S/cm, equivalent to about 11 orders of magnitude. The orthogonally interconnected GWF structure means immediate transition from the insulating polymer to conductive composites, regardless of graphene content, especially benefited from the defect-free GWF structure prepared in this study. When the graphene content was gradually increased to 0.62 wt%, however, it did not proportionally increase, but rather saturated, reaching ~ 0.18 S/cm. It is found previously that few-layer graphene presented even higher electrical conductivities than multi-layer graphene for freestanding 3D GF and GF/PDMS composites: an optimal average number of graphene layer corresponding to the maximum conductivity was identified to be about five [14].

A comparison of electrical conductivities between the similar epoxy-matrix composites containing 2D and 3D graphene, 1D carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and carbon nanofibers (CNFs) is shown in Figure 4(b). The current GWF/epoxy composites revealed phenomenal electrical conductivities at relative low filler contents, which are at least 3 orders of magnitude higher than those of GNP [15], rGO [16], CNTs [17, 18] and CNFs [19], benefiting from the conductive networks naturally formed by graphene

tubes. Compared to the 3D GA/epoxy system [13], the GWF/epoxy composites boasted more than 10 times higher electrical conductivities for a given graphene content, placing the latter system the second most conductive after the 3D GF/epoxy system [3]. The main reasons for the above observations are that the CVD-grown GFs or GWF are interconnected by graphene tubes to form inherent percolation, and do not require a reduction process to remove the insulating oxygenated functional groups to restore the electrical conductivity.

Figure 4: (a) In-plane electrical conductivities of GWF/epoxy composites; and (b) comparison of electrical conductivities of epoxy-based composites containing graphene, CNTs and CNFs.

3.3 Fracture toughness and tensile properties

The porous epoxy and GWF/epoxy composites are anisotropic in terms of geometry and properties because the hollow tubes are arranged in two orthogonal directions. As such, the effect of orientation against the loading direction should be taken into account when studying the fracture behavior and mechanical properties of the composites. The specimens prepared in three different orientations were tested in this work, namely, one consisting of single layer of 0°, the second with single layer of 45° and the last one with two layers each of 0° and 45°. Figure 5(a) shows the fracture toughness of solid epoxy, porous epoxy and single layer GWF/epoxy composites plotted as a function of graphene content. The fracture toughness of solid epoxy was 1.07 MPa·m^{1/2}, which is consistent with reported values of epoxy systems [20]. When the hollow tubes were aligned perpendicular or parallel to the applied load, i.e. 0°, the porous epoxy without graphene increased to 1.21 MPa·m^{1/2}, about 13% higher than that of the solid epoxy, indicating a beneficial effect of the porous structure. The K_{Ic} values of the GWF/epoxy composites gradually increased to 1.67 MPa·m^{1/2} at 0.62 wt% graphene, approximately 38% and 57% enhancements against the porous epoxy and solid epoxy counterparts, respectively. The enhancement of fracture toughness arose from crack-tip blunting due to the presence of the pores and graphene tubes in the composite. When the tubes were positioned 45° to the applied force, the porous epoxy and the composites presented slightly higher fracture toughness than those with the 0° configuration for all graphene volume fractions studied. The toughness of the porous epoxy and 0.62 wt% GWF/epoxy composite were 1.34 and 1.78 MPa·m^{1/2}, corresponding to about 25% and 67% increase compared to the solid epoxy, respectively. Figure 5(b) exhibits the fracture toughness of GWF/epoxy double-layer composites with 0°/45° mixed tube orientations. As expected, their fracture toughness values remained between those of the composites made from two layers stacked in the 0° and 45° directions.

Figure 5: Mode I fracture toughness K_{IC} of (a) GWF/epoxy composites loaded in two different directions; and (b) GWF/epoxy composites containing layers of 0° and 45° as a function of graphene content.

Figure 6 presents the tensile strength and Young's modulus of the epoxy and GWF/epoxy composites with two different orientations. In contrast to the aforementioned fracture toughness, the porous epoxy was sharply weaker and less stiff than the solid epoxy, mainly due to the presence of hollow tubes of a large volume fraction which disturbed the stress transfer through the bulk matrix. With the incorporation of graphene, the mechanical properties of the composites increased compared to the porous epoxy. At 0.62 wt% graphene, the tensile strengths of the composite with 0° and 45° were about 12% and 16% higher than those of the solid epoxy. The difference in strength between the composites with different graphene tube orientations was generally larger at low graphene contents. Relative to the obvious changes in strength, the Young's modulus of the composites showed only moderate improvements and the difference between the two orientations were very small.

Figure 6: (a) Tensile strength and (b) Young's modulus of solid epoxy, porous epoxy and GWF/epoxy composites as a function of graphene content.

3.4 Toughening mechanisms

Figure 7 shows the schematics of crack propagation in the solid epoxy and the GWF/epoxy composites with initial cracks. The crack in the solid epoxy propagated right through the specimen, breaking into two pieces catastrophically (Figure 7a) due to its brittle nature. As a result, the fracture toughness was low. In the porous epoxy and GWF/epoxy composites, the crack tip extended quickly in the epoxy matrix before it encountered the hollow tubes with or without graphene layers wrapped around them. It is interesting to note that the cracks always propagated along the hollow tubes

regardless of whether the tubes were oriented 0° or 45° against the loading direction (Figure 7b-c). Based on these observations, the crack-graphene tube interactions during the fracture tests are described as follows. (i) The hollow tubes function as a discrete phase to terminate the crack path and change the propagation direction [21]. (ii) Upon reaching the hollow tubes, the crack tip becomes blunted by the tubes and the graphene layers. (iii) The hollow tubes decrease the stress-concentration at the crack tip, requiring higher external loads for further crack propagation [22]. (iv) Once the barriers by the tubes and graphene walls are overcome, the cracks tear open the tubes along the tube axial direction. (v) The graphene layers functioned as external walls to hold the hollow tubes, and the debonding between the matrix and graphene may require additional energies to dissipate.

Figure 7: Schematics of fracture process in (a) solid epoxy, (b-c) GWF/epoxy composites with two different tube orientations. The black lines are the initial cracks, and the red lines show the crack propagation paths.

The *in situ* examination of the fracture process under the microscope offered an insight into crack propagation in the composites. It was found that the crack propagation behavior was very much sensitive to the direction of tubes against the external force. In the composites with the tubes running 0° and 90° directions, the crack propagation was limited by the tubes transverse to the running crack. Once there was a sufficient driving force, then the crack jumped leaving a 'step-shape' and propagated straight along the 90° direction (Figure 7b). In the composites with the tubes arranged 45° to the external load, the crack propagation was restricted immediately by the first hollow tube encountered and the crack paths became 'zig-zag shape' (Figure 7c). The driving force for tearing open the hollow tubes were not normal to the external force, meaning that a higher applied load was needed for crack propagation, thus higher fracture toughness than the 0° samples.

The fracture occurs along the hollow tubes in the tensile test and the effect of orientation on tensile strength was much the same as its effect on fracture toughness. In the composites with 45°, the deformation between matrix and graphene tubes needs higher applied load to provide driving force. Obvious enhancements are observed in samples with 45° than the ones with 0° orientation. The modulus of composites depends on the modulus and fractions of each component of the composite system. In porous epoxy and GWF/epoxy composites, the hollow tubes marginally weakened the matrix and made little contributions to the modulus. After addition of graphene layers, the reinforced graphene tubes restored the strength and modulus of the composites at high graphene contents.

Distinct and interesting features were identified from the fracture surfaces of the specimens, as shown in Figure 8. Compared to the smooth fracture surface of the solid epoxy, the porous epoxy showed a microscopically rougher surface; especially around the hollow tubes where the crack tips tended to become blunted before tearing open the tubes along their axes. The deformation and collapse of hollow tubes, and the increasing roughness mean a high toughness of the porous epoxy. With the

reinforcement of graphene, the fracture surface became rougher and there was strong evidence of significant deformation of the matrix surrounding the graphene tubes (Figures 8 (c) and (d)). The strong/stiff graphene layers significantly toughened the hollow tubes, requiring more energy to dissipate during the tearing of the graphene-lined tubes. The interfacial debonding of graphene layers at high graphene content, especially in the absence of any prior functionalization, (Figure 8 (d)) may also contribute to higher fracture toughness.

Figure 8: SEM images of fracture surfaces of (a) solid epoxy, (b) porous epoxy, (c-d) GWF/epoxy composites with 0.19 and 0.62 wt% graphene contents. The crack propagation direction is from left to right.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The present study reports the synthesis of interconnected planar GWF by a template-based CVD process. GWF/epoxy composites were prepared by directly infiltrating epoxy resin onto GWF, forming a porous structure after Ni template etching. The GWF functioned as efficient electrically conductive and toughening filler, improving the electrical, mechanical and fracture properties of the epoxy-based composites.

The GWF/epoxy composites showed an electrical conductivity of 0.15 S/cm at 0.19 wt% graphene and reach 0.18 S/cm when the graphene content was increased to 0.62 wt%. Conductive networks formed by the orthogonal hollow graphene tubes serve as conductive channel to improve the electrical conductivities of the composites. The orientations of hollow tubes in the porous epoxy and GWF/epoxy composites were taken into consideration when the fracture behavior and mechanical properties were characterized. The porous epoxy processed a fracture toughness of 1.21 and 1.34 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ with 0° and 45° orientations, about 13% and 25% enhancements against the solid epoxy, respectively. For the GWF/epoxy composites, K_{Ic} gradually increased to 1.67 and 1.78 $\text{MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ at 0.62 wt% graphene with 0° and 45° orientations, corresponding to 57% and 67% surges compared to the solid epoxy. With 0.62 wt% graphene, the tensile strengths of the composites with these two orientations were about 12% and 16% higher than the solid epoxy. Blunting at the crack tip and the resistance for crack propagation caused by the hollow tubes were mainly responsible for the considerable improvement in fracture toughness.

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